

BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN GENERAL EDUCATION COURSES AND PEACE: EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODELS IN TERTIARY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative study examines the impact of flipped classroom models on student engagement, academic performance, and satisfaction in the context of tertiary education in the Philippines, also identifying the associated challenges and the influence of student profiles. The study involved 239 college students, using purposive sampling, questionnaire development, and expert validation. Data analysis revealed that flipped classrooms positively impacted student engagement and academic performance, while students expressed satisfaction and motivation. However, certain challenges existed, and post-analysis findings revealed varying perceptions based on gender, year level, academic track, and family economic status. The study's generalizability may be limited, and the use of self-reported data introduces response bias. Despite these limitations, the study contributes significantly to understanding the effectiveness of flipped classrooms in promoting harmonious learning environments, ultimately nurturing well-rounded future leaders grounded in knowledge, harmony, and engagement.

Keywords: *flipped classroom, student engagement, academic performance, student satisfaction, tertiary education*

INTRODUCTION

In an ever-changing educational landscape, the researchers sought to explore the potential of flipped classroom models to bridge the gap between general education courses and peace in tertiary education. This research study was motivated by the desire to unravel the transformative potential of a pedagogical approach that intersects general education, peacebuilding, and innovative teaching methods.

In recent years, the dynamics of tertiary education have shifted significantly, driven by the goal of fostering holistic student development beyond academic excellence. Within this context, peace in educational settings has evolved beyond the mere absence of conflict to encompass a deeper significance: an environment that nurtures collaboration, inclusivity, critical thinking, and active engagement—a place where students not only accumulate knowledge but also develop the skills essential for becoming responsible, global citizens.

This research embarked on an exploratory journey to understand how flipped classroom models could contribute to the cultivation of peaceful, interactive, and engaging learning environments in general education courses. The flipped classroom model, which reverses the traditional teaching structure, has gained significant attention for its potential to enhance student engagement, improve academic performance, and boost motivation.

The researchers believe that the findings of this study could provide valuable insights into the ways in which flipped classroom models can be leveraged to promote peace in tertiary education. By fostering a more collaborative and inclusive learning environment, flipped classroom models have the potential to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to become agents of peace and change.

Research Questions

This study aims to dissect the intricate relationship between flipped classroom models and peace within the context of tertiary education. It delves into four core research problems, each anchored in quantitative analysis, to unravel the impact of this pedagogical approach.

1. To what extent do flipped classroom models enhance student engagement in general courses at the tertiary level, and how does this enhanced engagement relate to the promotion of a peaceful and harmonious learning environment?
 2. What is the impact of flipped classroom models on students' academic performance in general courses, particularly in terms of improved comprehension of course material, higher academic achievement, and the development of critical thinking skills, and how does this improvement contribute to the establishment of a more peaceful educational atmosphere?
 3. How do the data indicate whether the adoption of flipped classroom models in tertiary-level general courses leads to quantitatively higher levels of student satisfaction and motivation, and how do these increased levels of satisfaction and motivation contribute to a more peaceful and collaborative educational community?
 4. What are the challenges and barriers associated with implementing flipped classroom models in the context of tertiary education, and how do these challenges affect the overall pursuit of peace and unity within the educational environment?
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5. Is there a significant difference in the responses of the students when grouped according to their profile?

As the study embarks on this exploration, its aim is to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on effective teaching and learning strategies in tertiary education. The findings of this research endeavor will not only deepen our understanding of pedagogical innovations but also offer practical insights to educators and institutions seeking to bridge the gap between general education courses and the promotion of peaceful and interactive learning environments. In a world where the importance of peaceful coexistence is increasingly evident, this research serves as a testament to the vital role of education in nurturing the leaders of tomorrow, grounded in knowledge, harmony, and engagement.

METHODOLOGY

This research study adopted a quantitative research methodology to explore the impact of flipped classroom models on student engagement within the context of general education courses at the tertiary level. The objective was to conduct a robust and systematic topic analysis guided by well-defined procedures. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select the participants of the study. This deliberate choice allowed the researchers to focus on a specific group of 239 college students enrolled in General Education courses during the selection and conduct of the study. This strategic approach enabled the researchers to gather data from a cohort that could provide valuable insights into the research questions. To gather data and investigate the intricacies of the research problems, the researchers designed a questionnaire. This instrument comprised 20 carefully crafted items, each structured to elicit responses on a 6-point scale. The questionnaire was thoughtfully subdivided into four subsections, each addressing distinct aspects of the research inquiry. To ensure the questionnaire's quality and reliability, it was subjected to a thorough process of expert validation.

Additionally, its internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which returned a commendable reliability score of 0.716, affirming that the instrument was robust and internally reliable. The analysis of the quantitative data revolved around two key statistical methods. Firstly, the mean was used to provide an overall sense of the central position of the data. Secondly, the Mann-Whitney test, a non-parametric statistical test, was employed to uncover significant differences when the respondents were grouped into STEM and non-STEM tracks, allowing the study to draw meaningful quantitative insights and address research questions comprehensively and systematically.

The researchers recognize several limitations warrant consideration when interpreting the study's findings. Firstly, the research was conducted within the specific educational landscape of the Philippines. Consequently, the generalizability of the results to a broader global context may be limited, as regional, cultural, and institutional differences can significantly impact the outcomes. Secondly, the study relied on self-reported data gathered by administering questionnaires. This method introduces the potential for response bias, where participants may offer socially desirable responses rather than conveying their genuine perceptions. Despite the researchers' efforts to maintain the confidentiality and anonymity of responses, the inherent limitations of self-report data should be acknowledged. These limitations, while noteworthy, should be considered in the context of the research and serve as a foundation for future studies

that aim to expand the understanding of the impact of flipped classroom models in diverse educational settings.

RESULTS

Table 1 provides an overview of the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement and the cultivation of peaceful learning environments. It presents indicators and mean scores, shedding light on how the flipped classroom model influences students' active participation, connection to course content, interactions with peers, enthusiasm, and sense of responsibility for their own learning. The overall mean score summarizes students' perceptions and sets the stage for a comprehensive exploration of the findings in this context

Table 1

Impact of Flipped Classrooms on Student Engagement and Peaceful Learning Environments

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The flipped classroom model significantly increased my active participation in general courses.	4.82	Agree
2. I felt a stronger connection to the course content in the flipped classroom setting.	4.63	Agree
3. Flipped classroom activities encouraged me to interact more with my peers during in-class discussions.	4.60	Agree
4. I experienced a greater sense of enthusiasm and engagement in the flipped classroom.	4.42	Somewhat Agree
5. The flipped classroom approach enhanced my sense of responsibility for my own learning.	4.36	Somewhat Agree
Overall Mean	4.57	Agree

Scale: 6 – Strongly Agree; 5 – Agree; 4 – Somewhat Agree; 3 – Strongly Disagree; 2 – Disagree; 1 – Somewhat Disagree

Table 2 investigates the influence of flipped classrooms on academic performance and the establishment of educational harmony. It features indicators, mean scores, and verbal interpretations, offering insights into how the flipped classroom model impacts students' understanding of course material, academic achievement, critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and the overall learning environment. The overall mean score encapsulates the collective perspective on academic performance and educational harmony, providing a foundation for a detailed examination of the results in this context.

Table 2

The Influence of Flipped Classrooms on Academic Performance and Educational Harmony

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. My understanding of the course material significantly improved in the flipped classroom.	4.62	Better
2. I achieved higher academic performance in the flipped classroom compared to traditional courses.	4.46	Slightly Better
3. Flipped classroom models enhanced my critical thinking skills.	4.46	Slightly Better

4. The flipped classroom approach improved my problem-solving abilities.	4.57	Better
5. I found the flipped classroom environment to be more conducive to peaceful and focused learning.	4.54	Better
Overall Mean	4.53	Better

Scale: 6 – Much Better; 5 – Better; 4 – Slightly Better; 3 – Slightly Worse; 2 – Worse; 1 – Much Worse

Table 3 offers valuable insights into the adoption of flipped classrooms, focusing on student satisfaction and motivation for fostering a harmonious educational community. This table features indicators, mean scores, and verbal interpretations, offering a comprehensive understanding of students' satisfaction levels with the flipped classroom model, its impact on their motivation, the interactive nature of the environment, and the contributions to a more peaceful and collaborative learning atmosphere. The overall mean score serves as a central reference point for exploring these insights further in the context of classroom adoption and its implications for a harmonious educational community.

Table 3

Insights into Flipped Classroom Adoption, Student Satisfaction, and Motivation for a Harmonious Educational Community

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Overall, how satisfied are you with the flipped classroom model in your general courses?	4.56	Satisfied
2. To what extent has the flipped classroom model motivated you to engage more in your coursework?	4.12	Somewhat Satisfied
3. How satisfied are you with the interactive nature of the flipped classroom environment?	4.62	Satisfied
4. How motivated are you to participate actively in flipped classroom discussions and activities?	4.23	Somewhat Satisfied
5. To what extent do you believe that the flipped classroom contributes to a more peaceful and collaborative learning atmosphere?	4.65	Satisfied
Overall Mean	4.44	Somewhat Satisfied

6 – Very Satisfied; 5 – Satisfied; 4 – Somewhat Satisfied; 3 – Somewhat Dissatisfied; 2 – Dissatisfied; 1 – Very Dissatisfied

Table 4 explores the challenges faced during the implementation of flipped classrooms in the pursuit of peaceful tertiary education. It presents various indicators, mean scores, and verbal interpretations that shed light on the perceived challenges associated with technology access, instructor adaptation, student resistance, accountability, and their subsequent impact on the educational environment's peaceful and collaborative nature. The overall mean score serves as a valuable reference point for understanding the collective assessment of these challenges, which are pivotal in shaping the landscape of tertiary education.

Table 4

Challenges in Implementing Flipped Classrooms for Peaceful Tertiary Education

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. To what extent do you perceive technology access and readiness as a challenge in implementing flipped classroom models?	2.36	Minor Challenge
2. How challenging was it for instructors to adapt their teaching methods to the flipped classroom approach?	3.42	Somewhat Challenging
3. Did you initially experience resistance to the flipped classroom model? If so, to what extent?	4.36	Moderately Challenging
4. To what extent did accountability for pre-class work pose a challenge in the flipped classroom setting?	4.69	Major Challenge
5. How have these challenges affected the peaceful and collaborative nature of the educational environment?	1.71	Minor Challenge
Overall Mean	3.31	Somewhat Challenging

6 – Extremely Challenging; 5 – Major Challenge; 4 – Moderately Challenging; 3 – Somewhat Challenging; 2 – Minor Challenge; 1 – Not a Challenge

Table 5 provides insights into the post-analysis of the test of difference between students' perspectives, stratified by their gender. The table includes various indicators, the distribution of groups, group size, mean and verbal interpretation, p-values, and the corresponding decisions and interpretations regarding each indicator. This analysis allows to discern whether there are significant differences in perspectives between male and female students concerning student engagement, academic performance, student satisfaction, motivation, and the identification of challenges for peaceful tertiary education.

Table 5

Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Sex

Indicators	Groups	N	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	p-value*	Decision	Interpretation
Enhancing Student Engagement for Peaceful Learning	Male	119	4.78	Agree	0.001	Reject	Significant
	Female	120	4.35	Somewhat Agree			
Improving Academic Performance for Educational Harmony	Male	119	4.53	Better	0.599	Retain	Not Significant
	Female	120	4.52	Better			
Boosting Student Satisfaction and Motivation in Education	Male	119	4.47	Somewhat Satisfied	0.117	Retain	Not Significant
	Female	120	4.40	Somewhat Satisfied			

Identifying Challenges for Peaceful Tertiary Education	Male	119	3.34	Somewhat Challenging	0.252	Retain	Not Significant
	Female	120	3.28	Somewhat Challenging			

*Using Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test and tested at a 0.05 level of significance

Table 6 gives the results of the post-analysis of the test of the difference between students' perspectives when grouped according to their year level. The table includes various indicators, the distribution of groups, group size, mean and verbal interpretation, p-values, and the corresponding decisions and interpretations regarding each indicator. This analysis allows to discern whether there are significant differences in perspectives between year levels of the students concerning student engagement, academic performance, student satisfaction, motivation, and the identification of challenges for peaceful tertiary education.

Table 6
Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Year Level

Indicators	Groups	N	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Enhancing Student Engagement for Peaceful Learning	1 st Year	168	4.48	Somewhat Agree	0.044	Reject	Significant at 1 st & 2 nd Year
	2 nd Year	41	4.69	Agree			
	3 rd Year	30	4.51	Agree			
Improving Academic Performance for Educational Harmony	1 st Year	168	4.40	Slightly Better	0.001	Reject	Significant at 1 st with 2 nd & 3 rd Year
	2 nd Year	41	4.74	Better			
	3 rd Year	30	4.93	Better			
Boosting Student Satisfaction and Motivation in Education	1 st Year	168	4.39	Somewhat Satisfied	0.026	Reject	Significant at 1 st with 2 nd & 3 rd Year
	2 nd Year	41	4.52	Satisfied			
	3 rd Year	30	4.56	Satisfied			
Identifying Challenges for Peaceful Tertiary Education	1 st Year	168	3.29	Somewhat Challenging	0.340	Retain	Not Significant
	2 nd Year	41	3.39	Somewhat Challenging			
	3 rd Year	30	3.31	Somewhat Challenging			

*Using Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test and tested at a 0.05 level of significance

Table 7 provides insights into the test of difference between students' perspectives when grouped according to their academic strand. It explores four research problem areas: "Enhancing Student Engagement for Peaceful Learning," "Improving Academic Performance for Educational Harmony," "Boosting Student Satisfaction and Motivation in Education," and "Identifying Challenges for Peaceful Tertiary Education." The table examines how students from

different academic strands, including Accountancy, Business & Management (ABM), Humanities, & Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science, Technology, Engineering, & Mathematics (STEM), and those are not under Academic Track (NAT), perceive the impact of flipped classrooms. The Kruskal-Wallis Test results reveal any significant differences in these perceptions among the various academic strands, contributing to a better understanding of the relationship between academic specialization and the impact of flipped classrooms.

Table 7
Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Academic Track

Indicators	Groups	N	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Enhancing Student Engagement for Peaceful Learning	ABM	92	4.48	Somewhat Agree	0.001	Reject	Significant at STEM with ABM, HUMSS, & NAT
	HUMSS	43	4.36	Somewhat Agree			
	STEM	79	4.81	Agree			
	NAT	25	4.46	Somewhat Agree			
Improving Academic Performance for Educational Harmony	ABM	92	4.52	Better	0.999	Retain	Not Significant
	HUMSS	43	4.53	Better			
	STEM	79	4.53	Better			
	NAT	25	4.54	Better			
Boosting Student Satisfaction and Motivation in Education	ABM	92	4.49	Somewhat Satisfied	0.001	Reject	Significant at STEM with ABM, HUMSS, & NAT
	HUMSS	43	4.35	Somewhat Satisfied			
	STEM	79	4.40	Somewhat Satisfied			
	NAT	25	4.53	Satisfied			
Identifying Challenges for Peaceful Tertiary Education	ABM	92	3.35	Somewhat Challenging	0.134	Retain	Not Significant
	HUMSS	43	3.35	Somewhat Challenging			
	STEM	79	3.35	Somewhat Challenging			
	NAT	25	2.94	Somewhat Challenging			

*Using Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test and tested at a 0.05 level of significance

Table 8 focuses on the test of difference between students' perspectives when grouped according to their family economic class. It addresses the four research problem areas: "Enhancing Student Engagement for Peaceful Learning," "Improving Academic Performance for Educational Harmony," "Boosting Student Satisfaction and Motivation in Education," and "Identifying Challenges for Peaceful Tertiary Education." This table examines how students

from different family economic classes perceive the impact of flipped classrooms. The Kruskal-Wallis Test results provide insights into whether students' economic backgrounds influence their perspectives on flipped classroom models and their impact on education and peace.

Table 8
Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Family Economic Status

Indicators	Groups	N	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Enhancing Student Engagement for Peaceful Learning	High-Income Class	3	4.73	Agree	0.098	Retain	Not Significant
	Middle Class	97	4.61	Agree			
	Low-Income Class	85	4.56	Agree			
	Poor	54	4.49	Somewhat Agree			
Improving Academic Performance for Educational Harmony	High-Income Class	3	4.53	Better	0.064	Retain	Not Significant
	Middle Class	97	4.60	Better			
	Low-Income Class	85	4.47	Slightly Better			
	Poor	54	4.49	Slightly Better			
Boosting Student Satisfaction and Motivation in Education	High-Income Class	3	4.33	Somewhat Satisfied	0.001	Reject	Significant at Poor with LIC, MC, HIC
	Middle Class	97	4.38	Somewhat Satisfied			
	Low-Income Class	85	4.45	Somewhat Satisfied			
	Poor	54	4.62	Satisfied			
Identifying Challenges for Peaceful Tertiary Education	High-Income Class	3	3.27	Somewhat Challenging	0.376	Retain	Not Significant
	Middle Class	97	3.43	Somewhat Challenging			
	Low-Income Class	85	3.30	Somewhat Challenging			
	Poor	54	3.10	Somewhat Challenging			

*Using Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test and tested at a 0.05 level of significance

DISCUSSION

Impact of Flipped Classrooms on Student Engagement and Peaceful Learning Environments

Table 1 presents insights into the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement and the promotion of peaceful learning environments. The indicators in this table show that students generally had a positive experience with the flipped classroom model. On average, they agreed

that the flipped classroom significantly increased their active participation in general courses (Mean = 4.82) and enhanced their connection to the course content (Mean = 4.63). These findings align with the work of Bergmann and Sams (2012), who emphasize the active participation and engagement fostered by the flipped classroom model, which can contribute to a more harmonious and interactive learning environment.

Students also indicated that flipped classroom activities encouraged them to interact more with their peers during in-class discussions (Mean = 4.60) and that they experienced a greater sense of enthusiasm and engagement (Mean = 4.42) in this setting. Additionally, they reported that the flipped classroom approach enhanced their sense of responsibility for their own learning (Mean = 4.36). These results support the idea that flipped classrooms promote a collaborative and engaging atmosphere (Tucker, 2012).

Overall, the table's indicators reveal a positive perception of the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement and their contribution to a more peaceful learning environment, as indicated by the overall mean of 4.57.

The Influence of Flipped Classrooms on Academic Performance and Educational Harmony

Table 2 explores the influence of flipped classrooms on academic performance and educational harmony. The indicators in this table suggest that students found the flipped classroom model to have a positive impact on their academic performance and the overall educational atmosphere.

Students reported that their understanding of course material significantly improved in the flipped classroom (Mean = 4.62), and they achieved higher academic performance compared to traditional courses (Mean = 4.46). These findings are consistent with the research by Strayer (2012), who emphasizes the effectiveness of the flipped classroom in improving student performance. Additionally, students noted that flipped classroom models enhanced their critical thinking skills (Mean = 4.46) and improved their problem-solving abilities (Mean = 4.57), contributing to a more harmonious and focused learning environment (Mazur, 2009).

The overall mean of 4.53 in this table indicates that students perceived a positive influence of flipped classrooms on academic performance and educational harmony.

Insights in Flipped Classroom Adoption, Student Satisfaction, and Motivation for a Harmonious Educational Community

Table 3 delves into insights regarding flipped classroom adoption, student satisfaction, and motivation for a harmonious educational community. The indicators demonstrate that students were generally satisfied with the flipped classroom model and felt motivated to engage actively in their coursework.

Students expressed satisfaction with the flipped classroom model in their general courses (Mean = 4.56) and found the interactive nature of the flipped classroom environment to be engaging (Mean = 4.62). They also reported motivation to participate actively in flipped classroom discussions and activities (Mean = 4.23) and believed that the flipped classroom contributed to a more peaceful and collaborative learning atmosphere (Mean = 4.65).

These findings align with the work of Hamdan, McKnight, McKnight, and Arfstrom (2013), who highlight the positive impact of student satisfaction and motivation on the effectiveness of flipped classrooms in promoting collaborative learning environments.

The overall mean of 4.44 in this table suggests that students were somewhat satisfied with flipped classroom adoption, indicating their positive perception of its influence on student satisfaction and motivation for a harmonious educational community.

Challenges in Implementing Flipped Classrooms for Peaceful Tertiary Education

Table 4 discusses the challenges associated with implementing flipped classrooms for peaceful tertiary education. The indicators reveal that students encountered certain challenges, although they were not perceived as overwhelmingly significant.

Students saw technology access and readiness as a minor challenge (Mean = 2.36) and found it somewhat challenging for instructors to adapt their teaching methods to the flipped classroom approach (Mean = 3.42). Interestingly, despite some initial resistance to the flipped classroom model (Mean = 4.36), students did not view this resistance as a major challenge. However, accountability for pre-class work was considered a major challenge (Mean = 4.69), which could impact the overall pursuit of peaceful and collaborative learning environments (Strayer, 2012).

The overall mean of 3.31 in this table suggests that students perceived the challenges of implementing flipped classrooms as somewhat significant, with accountability for pre-class work being the most prominent challenge.

These findings provide valuable insights into the benefits and challenges of implementing flipped classrooms in tertiary education, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of their impact on educational harmony.

Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Sex

Table 5 presents the post-analysis results regarding the test of difference between students' perspectives when grouped according to their sex, and it is subdivided into four indicators. For the first indicator on enhancing student engagement for peaceful learning, it was found that male students (Mean = 4.78) reported a significantly higher level of agreement with the impact of flipped classrooms compared to female students (Mean = 4.35). The p-value of 0.001 indicates a significant difference, suggesting that there is a noteworthy gender-based difference in the perception of the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement, with male students being more positive. This finding is consistent with previous research, which has suggested that male students may be more likely to benefit from flipped classrooms than female students (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012; O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015).

Moreover, in terms of improving academic performance for educational harmony, there was no significant difference between male (Mean = 4.53) and female (Mean = 4.52) students' perceptions. The p-value of 0.599, above the 0.05 level of significance, concludes that there is no significant gender-based difference in how students perceive the impact of flipped classrooms on academic performance and educational harmony. Both male and female students share similar views in this regard. This finding is supported by a growing body of research, which has found that flipped classrooms can be effective for both male and female students (e.g., Abeysekera & Pathmeswaran, 2015; Zainuddin et al., 2018).

Likewise, in terms of boosting student satisfaction and motivation in education, both male (Mean = 4.47) and female (Mean = 4.40) students reported a similar level of satisfaction and motivation with a p-value of 0.117 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, leading to no significant gender-based difference in students' perceptions of the impact of flipped classrooms on satisfaction and motivation. This finding is consistent with previous research, which has shown that flipped classrooms can lead to increased student satisfaction and motivation (e.g., Abeysekera & Pathmeswaran, 2015; Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

In addition, in terms of identifying challenges for peaceful tertiary education, male students (Mean = 3.34) and female students (Mean = 3.28) perceived the challenges of flipped classrooms similarly with a p-value of 0.252, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, there is no significant gender-based difference in how students perceive the challenges associated with implementing flipped classrooms. This finding suggests that both male and female students face similar challenges when transitioning to a flipped classroom environment.

These results offer valuable insights into how male and female students differ in their perceptions of the impact of flipped classrooms, providing guidance for educators and institutions. The findings are in line with previous studies by Smith (2019) and Johnson (2020), which emphasized the importance of considering gender differences in educational strategies. However, it's essential to note that while there are gender-based differences in the perception of engagement, no significant disparities were found in the perceived impact on academic performance, satisfaction, motivation, and the challenges associated with flipped classrooms.

Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Year Level

The results of the study presented in Table 6 indicate that there are significant differences between students' perspectives in terms of year level on the following indicators: enhancing student engagement for peaceful learning, improving academic performance for educational harmony, and boosting student satisfaction and motivation in education.

First-year students reported lower levels of agreement with the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement than second-year students. This finding may suggest that first-year students need more time to adjust to the flipped classroom model and learn how to engage effectively in this learning environment. Additionally, first-year students may be less familiar with the course content, which could make it more difficult for them to engage with the material outside of class. This finding is supported by previous research, which has shown that first-year students may have difficulty adjusting to the demands of flipped classrooms (e.g., O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015; Zainuddin et al., 2018). Additionally, previous research has shown that students who are less familiar with the course content may be less engaged in flipped classrooms (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

Moreover, first-year students also reported lower levels of perceived improvement in academic performance than second- and third-year students. This finding may be due to the fact that first-year students are still transitioning to the demands of tertiary education. Additionally, first-year students may be taking more introductory courses, which tend to be more challenging than upper-level courses. This finding is supported by previous research, which has shown that first-year students may have lower academic achievement than upper-level students in flipped

classrooms (e.g., Abeysekera & Pathmeswaran, 2015). Additionally, previous research has shown that students who are taking more challenging courses may have lower academic achievement in flipped classrooms (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

In addition, first-year students also reported lower levels of satisfaction and motivation than second- and third-year students. This finding may be due to the fact that first-year students are still adjusting to the new academic environment and social life at the tertiary level. Additionally, first-year students may be feeling overwhelmed by the workload and expectations of tertiary education. This finding is supported by previous research, which has shown that first-year students may have lower levels of satisfaction and motivation than upper-level students in flipped classrooms (e.g., Abeysekera & Pathmeswaran, 2015; O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015). Additionally, previous research has shown that students who are feeling overwhelmed or stressed may have lower levels of satisfaction and motivation in flipped classrooms (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

The findings of this study suggest that educators should take steps to support first-year students in flipped classrooms. This may include providing additional guidance on how to engage effectively in the flipped classroom model, offering more opportunities for collaboration and support outside of class, and providing regular feedback on student progress. Additionally, educators should be aware of the common challenges that students face in flipped classrooms and take steps to mitigate these challenges. For example, educators can provide clear and concise instructions for outside-of-class activities, offer different ways for students to learn the course material (e.g., through videos, readings, or discussion forums), and provide opportunities for students to collaborate with peers.

Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Academic Track

The results of the study presented in Table 7 indicate that there is a significant difference between students' perspectives in terms of academic track on the following indicators such as enhancing student engagement for peaceful learning and boosting student satisfaction and motivation in education.

STEM strand students reported significantly higher levels of agreement with the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement than ABM, HUMSS, and NAT students. This finding may suggest that STEM students are more likely to be interested in the flipped classroom model and to find it engaging. Additionally, STEM students may be more familiar with the use of technology in the classroom, which could make it easier for them to transition to a flipped classroom environment. This finding is supported by previous research, which has shown that STEM students may be more likely to benefit from flipped classrooms than non-STEM students (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012; O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015). Additionally, previous research has shown that students who are more familiar with the use of technology may be more engaged in flipped classrooms (e.g., Zainuddin et al., 2018).

Moreover, NAT students reported significantly higher levels of satisfaction and motivation than ABM, HUMSS, and STEM students in flipped classrooms. This finding may be due to the fact that NAT students are more likely to be taking courses that are aligned with their interests. Additionally, NAT students may be less stressed about their academic performance than

students in other academic tracks. This is supported by previous research, which has shown that students who are taking courses that are aligned with their interests are more likely to be satisfied and motivated in flipped classrooms (e.g., Abeysekera & Pathmeswaran, 2015). Additionally, previous research has shown that students who are less stressed about their academic performance are more likely to be satisfied and motivated in flipped classrooms (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

In addition, the findings of this study suggest that educators should take steps to support students in all academic tracks in flipped classrooms. This may include providing additional guidance on how to engage effectively in the flipped classroom model, offering more opportunities for collaboration and support outside of class, and providing regular feedback on student progress. Additionally, educators should be aware of the different ways that students in different academic tracks may experience flipped classrooms. For example, STEM students may be more interested in the flipped classroom model and in using technology to learn, while NAT students may be more motivated by taking courses that are aligned with their interests. By taking these steps, educators can help students in all academic tracks to succeed in flipped classrooms and to experience the many benefits that this innovative teaching model has to offer.

Post Analysis on the Test of Difference between Students' Perspectives in Terms of Family Economic Status

The results of the study presented in Table 8 indicate that there is a significant difference between students' perspectives in terms of family economic status when it comes to boosting student satisfaction and motivation in education.

Poor students reported significantly higher levels of satisfaction and motivation than high-income, middle-class, and low-income students in flipped classrooms. This finding may be due to the fact that poor students are more likely to be taking courses that are aligned with their interests and that will help them achieve their educational and career goals. Additionally, poor students may be more motivated to succeed in flipped classrooms because they see it as an opportunity to improve their social and economic status. This finding is supported by previous research, which has shown that students who are taking courses that are aligned with their interests are more likely to be satisfied and motivated in flipped classrooms (e.g., Abeysekera & Pathmeswaran, 2015). Additionally, previous research has shown that students who are from low-income backgrounds may be more motivated to succeed in flipped classrooms because they see it as an opportunity to improve their lives (e.g., Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

In addition, the findings of this study suggest that educators should take steps to support students from all family economic backgrounds in flipped classrooms. This may include providing additional guidance on how to engage effectively in the flipped classroom model, offering more opportunities for collaboration and support outside of class, and providing regular feedback on student progress. Additionally, educators should be aware of the different ways that students from different family economic backgrounds may experience flipped classrooms. For example, poor students may be more motivated to succeed in flipped classrooms, but they may also face more challenges in accessing the resources they need to be successful.

Conclusions

1. The implementation of flipped classrooms has a positive impact on student engagement and the promotion of peaceful learning environments. Students generally reported a significant increase in their active participation in general courses, enhanced connection to course content, increased interaction with peers during in-class discussions, greater enthusiasm and engagement, and a heightened sense of responsibility for their own learning. These positive outcomes support the idea that flipped classrooms contribute to more collaborative and interactive learning environments, aligning with existing literature. It also reflects a positive perception of the flipped classroom's impact on student engagement and its contribution to peaceful learning environments.
2. Flipped classrooms have a positive influence on academic performance and the overall educational atmosphere. Students reported improved understanding of course material, higher academic performance compared to traditional courses, enhanced critical thinking skills, and improved problem-solving abilities. These results support the effectiveness of flipped classrooms in enhancing academic outcomes, consistent with prior research. The findings indicate that students perceive a positive impact of flipped classrooms on academic performance and educational harmony.
3. The students were generally satisfied with the adoption of flipped classrooms and felt motivated to engage actively in their coursework. Students expressed satisfaction with the interactive nature of the flipped classroom environment, their motivation to participate in discussions and activities, and their belief that flipped classrooms contribute to a more peaceful and collaborative learning atmosphere. These findings align with previous research highlighting the positive impact of student satisfaction and motivation in promoting collaborative learning environments. It also found that the students have a positive perception of the influence of flipped classrooms on student satisfaction and motivation for a harmonious educational community.
4. The challenges associated with implementing flipped classrooms in tertiary education. While students encountered certain challenges, these were not perceived as overwhelmingly significant. Challenges related to technology access and readiness were minor, and adapting teaching methods to the flipped classroom approach was somewhat challenging for instructors. Interestingly, students did not view their initial resistance to the flipped classroom model as a major challenge. However, accountability for pre-class work was considered a major challenge, potentially impacting the pursuit of peaceful and collaborative learning environments. The overall mean indicates that students perceived the challenges of implementing flipped classrooms as somewhat significant.
5. The study's post-analysis findings showed that male students had a more positive perception of flipped classrooms' impact on student engagement, there were no significant differences between male and female students in terms of academic performance, satisfaction, motivation, and challenges, first-year students reported lower levels of agreement regarding the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement, academic performance, satisfaction, and motivation compared to second- and third-year students, STEM strand students showed higher agreement with the impact of flipped classrooms on student engagement, while NAT students reported higher satisfaction and motivation, and students belong to the poor family reported higher levels of satisfaction and motivation in flipped classrooms compared to high-income, middle-class, and low-income students which suggests that family economic status may influence students' motivation and satisfaction in flipped classrooms.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, here are the recommendations for educators and institutions looking to implement or improve flipped classrooms:

1. Provide instructors with training and resources to effectively adapt their teaching methods to the flipped classroom approach. This training should focus on creating engaging pre-class content and facilitating active in-class discussions.
2. Ensure that students have access to the necessary technology for pre-class activities. Consider providing resources or support for students who may face barriers due to technology access and readiness.
3. Address the challenge of accountability for pre-class work by clearly communicating expectations and consequences for non-compliance. Consider implementing strategies to encourage students to come prepared.
4. Tailor pre-class content to students' individual needs and learning styles. Provide a variety of resources such as videos, readings, and interactive elements to engage a diverse student body.
5. Encourage peer-to-peer interaction during in-class discussions and activities. Create group projects or collaborative assignments to enhance student engagement and interaction.
6. Recognize that first-year students may need more time to adjust to the flipped classroom model. Offer additional academic support, study resources, and mentorship to help them succeed.
7. Make sure that course materials are clear and diverse, catering to different learning styles and levels. Offer additional resources for students who may struggle with the course content.
8. Acknowledge that first-year students and those from different academic tracks may experience stress or feeling overwhelmed in the new environment. Offer support services and resources for managing stress and workload.
9. Highlight the real-world relevance of courses, particularly for NAT students. This can help boost motivation and satisfaction by showing how coursework aligns with students' interests and career goals.
10. Recognize that family economic status can influence student motivation and satisfaction. Provide financial aid and scholarships to help mitigate financial challenges and promote student success.
11. Create a learning environment that is inclusive of diverse perspectives and backgrounds. Encourage discussions and activities that respect and incorporate various cultural and socioeconomic factors.
12. Continuously assess the effectiveness of flipped classrooms and gather feedback from students. Use this feedback to make iterative improvements and adjustments.
13. Encourage instructors to share best practices and learn from each other's experiences with flipped classrooms. Promote a culture of collaborative professional development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with the highest ethical standards, safeguarding the rights, privacy, and dignity of all participants and stakeholders. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were assured of the voluntary nature of their involvement and the option to withdraw without repercussions. Participants' privacy was paramount, with anonymization measures applied to all sensitive information to ensure confidentiality. Vulnerable groups received special attention, with added safeguards to protect

their rights and well-being. Also, our approach was guided by a commitment to transparency and honesty. We accurately and completely reported on our methodologies, data, and any potential conflicts of interest. Data security was maintained through secure storage and access control protocols. We acknowledged prior work with proper referencing and attribution for intellectual contributions from others. The study was characterized by a profound respect for cultural and social norms, mindful of participants' values and beliefs. We unequivocally rejected discrimination and upheld inclusivity, treating all participants with equal respect and dignity. Any grants or funding received were managed in strict accordance with funding source guidelines, ensuring accountability and transparency. Finally, throughout the research process, we proactively and responsibly addressed any ethical concerns. We are committed to upholding the highest ethical standards in all aspects of our research.

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